

Weighted Generalizations of Some Fractional Integral Inequalities

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Abstract

In this study, first we will present an identity for differentiable functions involving a weight function. Then by using this equality, we obtain some weighted inequalities for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For this aim we will use some functional classes such as bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, etc. We also present several remarks and corollaries by the special choice of weight function.

1. Introduction

Many mathematicians have investigated the error upper bounds related to numerical integration formulas using different approaches. These error limitations are found by analyzing mathematical inequalities for a variety of function classes, such as Lipschitzian, bounded, and convex functions.

Dedic et al. [1] employ the Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities to build a set of inequalities in the case of the Maclaurin quadrature rules, and the results are used to provide specific error estimates. The results are applied to some error approximations for the Simpson 3/8 quadrature rules in the paper [2]. A number of Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality were investigated in the context of differentiable convex functions in the work [3]. Furthermore, using the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, some corrected Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities are considered in paper [4]. The paper [5] presents a set of Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities that apply Riemann Liouville fractional integrals to different function classes. These type of inequalities are constructed by bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions and fractional integrals of bounded variation. In paper [6], some weighted Newton-type inequalities are established for various classes of functions employing Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For more detail on various kinds of inequality, the reader is directed to [7-10] and the references therein.

The Maclaurin rule is equivalent to the corresponding dual Simpson’s 3/8 formula, and it is derived from the Maclaurin formula (refer to [10]).

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right].$$

The Maclaurin rule, which comes from the Maclaurin inequality, is comparable to the analogous dual Simpson’s 3/8 formula:

Theorem 1. Suppose that $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

The well-known Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals are explained as follows:

Definition 1. (See, [11],[12]) The Riemann–Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are presented by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

And

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. Here, f belongs to $L_1[a, b]$ and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the

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Gamma function defining as

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

The fractional integral reduces to the classical integral for the case of $\alpha = 1$.

Throughout the paper, we suppose that $w: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is an non-negative and continuous on $[a, b]$ and symmetric with respect to $\frac{a+b}{2}$ (i.e. $w(x) = w(a+b-x)$ for all $x \in [a, b]$). Now, let us define the functions W_1 and W_2 by

$$W_1(\alpha, t) = \int_t^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - u\right)^{\alpha-1} w(u) du$$

and

$$W_2(\alpha, t) = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t \left(u - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^{\alpha-1} w(u) du.$$

We have the following equalities since the function w is symmetric with regard to $\frac{a+b}{2}$; these equalities will be utilized frequently in the following sections:

$$\begin{aligned} W(\alpha) &:= W_1(\alpha, a) = W_2(\alpha, b) \\ &= \Gamma(\alpha) J_{b^-}^\alpha w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\ &= \Gamma(\alpha) J_{a^+}^\alpha w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} W_1(\alpha, t) &= W_2(\alpha, a+b-t), W_2(\alpha, t) \\ &= W_1(\alpha, a+b-t). \end{aligned}$$

Specifically, we also get

$$\begin{aligned} W(1) &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} w(x) dx = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b w(x) dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b w(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1. (See [13]) If $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) such that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$, then the equality

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ &- \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} [I_3 + I_4 - I_1 - I_2]$$

is valid. Here, Γ is Euler Gamma function and

$$\begin{cases} I_1 = \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} [W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] f'(t) dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] f'(t) dt \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] f'(t) dt, \\ I_4 = \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] f'(t) dt. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 1. Let us assume that the Lemma 1 contains all of its assumptions. Next, we have the subsequent equalities

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ &- \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] [f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)] dt \right. \\ &\left. + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] [f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)] dt \right] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

$$- \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} [W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt \right. \\ &\left. + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \left[W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

2. Weighted fractional Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities for bounded functions

In this section, we provide sundry weighted fractional Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities for bounded functions.

Theorem 2. Let us consider that the conditions of Lemma 1 hold. If there exist $m, M \in R$ such that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a+}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| dt \right] (M - m). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By using the equality (1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ & = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] \left[f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] \left[f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right] dt. \end{aligned}$$

By using the absolute value of (3), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a+}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| \left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right| dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

It is known that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$. Thus, we have

$$\left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2} \tag{4}$$

and

$$\left| f'(a+b-t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{5}$$

Let us consider (4) and (5). Then, it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a+}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f w\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| dt \right] (M - m). \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. If we consider $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Theorem 2, then we have the following fractional Euler–

Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \\ & - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha}} \left[J_{a+}^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ & \leq \frac{M-m}{4} [\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha)], \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_1(\alpha) & = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt \\ & = \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{1+\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{6}, & 0 < \alpha < \frac{\ln\left(\frac{1}{4}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)}, \\ \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1}, & \frac{\ln\left(\frac{1}{4}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)} < \alpha \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\Omega_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^{\alpha}) dt = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1}.$$

This is proved in paper [14, Theorem 7].

Corollary 2. Let us consider $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2. Then, we have the following weighted Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \int_a^b w(t) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_a^b w(t) f(t) dt \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq (M - m) \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t w(u) du - \frac{1}{8} \int_a^b w(u) du \right| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left(u - \frac{a+5b}{6} \right) w(u) du \right].$$

Remark 2. If we select $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Corollary 2, then the following Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{576} (M - m),$$

which is given in paper [14, Corollary 2].

Corollary 3. Under the conditions of Theorem 2, if there exist $M \in R^+$ such that $|f(t)| \leq M$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \leq M \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| dt \right].$$

3. Weighted fractional Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions

Now, we provide several weighted fractional Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities for the case of Lipschitzian functions.

Theorem 3. Let us consider that the assumptions of Lemma 1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \leq L \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right].$$

Proof. Using the fact that f' is L -Lipschitzian function, by the equality (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| |f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| |f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)| dt \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4} W(\alpha) \right| L |2t - (a+b)| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| L |2t - (a+b)| dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3. Note that $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Theorem 3. Then, the following fractional Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality is satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a^+}^\alpha f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{4} L \{ \Omega_3(\alpha) + \Omega_4(\alpha) \}.$$

Here,

$$\Omega_3(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{1}{18}, & 0 < \alpha < \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{18} - \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+2}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})} < \alpha \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t |t^\alpha - 1| dt = \frac{5}{18} - \frac{1}{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^{\alpha+2}.$$

This is proved in paper [14, Theorem 8].

Proof. By special choice of $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ and by changing variables, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{4}W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^\alpha \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{\alpha+1} \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} t |t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4}| dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{\alpha+1} \Omega_3(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^\alpha - \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^\alpha \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{\alpha+1} \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t |t^\alpha - 1| dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{\alpha+1} \Omega_4(\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3, then we have the following weighted Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] \int_a^b w(t) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_a^b w(t) f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq 2L \\ & \times \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t w(u) du - \frac{1}{8} \int_a^b w(u) du \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} w(u) \left[\left(u - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{b-a}{3} \right)^2 \right] du \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof is obvious from the fact that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t w(u) du - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b w(u) du \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left(\int_t^b w(u) du \right) \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\ &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \int_t^b \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) w(u) dt du \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^u \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) w(u) dt du \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} w(u) \left[\left(u - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{b-a}{3} \right)^2 \right] du. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4. Consider $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Corollary 4. Then, we have the following Euler–Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{475(b-a)^2}{20736} L, \end{aligned}$$

which is given in paper [14, Corollary 5].

4. Conclusions

In this section, state the main conclusions of the study.

Main results of the paper and its contribution can be reviewed. However, avoid duplicating the abstract. The importance of the work and future studies can be emphasized towards the end of this section.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The authors of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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